

DYEING OF TEXTILE MATERIALS WITH NATURAL DYES

¹Bekbatur Gulnur Baqytzhanqyzy, ²Dyussenbiyeva Kulmairam Zhamanbaevna,
³Alтынbaeva Ainur Tolendiqyzy

¹master's student, ATU, ²PhD, ATU, ³senior-lecturer, ATU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14177160>

Annotatsiya. Maqola tabiiy bo'yoqlardan foydalangan holda to'qimachilik materiallarini bo'yash jarayonini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Bunday bo'yoqlardan foydalanishning afzalliklari, jumladan, ularning ekologik xavfsizligi, biologik parchalanishi va allergiyaga qarshi xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Tabiiy bo'yoqlarning manbalari, ularni qo'llash texnologiyasi va bo'yash jarayonining asosiy bosqichlari tasvirlangan. Atrof-muhit va iste'molchilar salomatligi uchun tobora ortib borayotgan tashvish bilan tabiiy bo'yoqlar sintetik bo'yash usullariga muhim alternativaga aylanmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: tabiiy bo'yoqlar, to'qimachilik materiallari, ekologik barqarorlik, biologik parchalanish, allergiyaga qarshi xususiyatlar, bo'yash texnologiyasi.

Аннотация. Статья посвящена изучению процесса крашения текстильных материалов с использованием природных красителей. Рассматриваются преимущества использования таких красителей, включая их экологическую безопасность, биологическую разлагаемость и антиаллергенные свойства. Описаны источники природных красителей, технология их применения и основные этапы процесса крашения. В условиях растущей заботы об экологии и здоровье потребителей, природные красители становятся важной альтернативой синтетическим методам крашения.

Ключевые слова: природные красители, текстильные материалы, экологическая устойчивость, биологическая разлагаемость, антиаллергенные свойства, технология крашения.

Abstract. The article is devoted to the study of the process of dyeing textile materials using natural dyes. The advantages of using such dyes, including their environmental safety, biodegradability and anti-allergenic properties, are considered. The sources of natural dyes, the technology of their application and the main stages of the dyeing process are described. With growing concern for the environment and the health of consumers, natural dyes are becoming an important alternative to synthetic dyeing methods.

Keywords: natural dyes, textile materials, environmental sustainability, biodegradability, anti-allergenic properties, dyeing technology.

The use of natural dyes to dye textile materials has a long history and has attracted attention again in recent years due to its environmental sustainability and health safety. Natural dyes are derived from a variety of plant, animal, and mineral sources, such as tree bark, leaves, flowers, roots, insects, and minerals. Unlike synthetic dyes, natural dyes are usually safer for the environment and do not contain toxic chemicals [1,2].

Vegetable dyes are a complex mixture of extractable pigments and various substances. Thanks to this, a durable (permanent) color is achieved, which in some cases still cannot be achieved with the help of artificial chemical paints. Vegetable dyes in comparison with synthetic ones have a number of advantages when used in such light industries as carpet, fur, wool, silk, and many of them are indispensable in the production of food products [3,4].

The aim of the study is to develop a dyeing technology using natural dyes for protein and cellulose textile materials.

Advantages of using natural dyes:

1. Environmental safety: natural dyes do not contain hazardous chemical compounds and do not emit harmful substances during production and operation. This reduces the negative impact on the environment and minimizes air and water pollution.

2. Biodegradability: natural dye residues are easily degradable in the environment without causing pollution and toxin accumulation. This makes the dyeing process less harmful to ecosystems.

3. Anti-allergenic properties: fabrics dyed with natural dyes are less likely to cause allergic reactions, making them more suitable for use in clothing for people with sensitive skin, as well as in children's clothing and home textiles.

4. Natural and unique shades: natural dyes create soft, warm, and natural hues that are difficult to replicate with synthetic dyes. Each dyeing process using natural ingredients can produce unique results, making the fabric special and exclusive.

5. Reduced carbon footprint: the production of natural dyes requires less energy compared to the production of synthetic analogues. This helps reduce greenhouse gas emissions and helps in the fight against climate change.

Natural dyes are usually isolated from natural sources in the form of a mixture of compounds of different chemical nature, the composition of which depends on the source and technology of production, and therefore it is often difficult to ensure its consistency.

1. Vegetable dyes: Indian Indigo (from leaves *Indigofera tinctoria*) for blue, madder (*Rubia tinctorum*) for red, turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) for yellow, figure 1.
2. Animal dyes: carmine, derived from cochineal, is used to create rich red hues.
3. Mineral dyes: used to produce more neutral and muted hues.

Figure 1- Vegetable dyes

Technology of dyeing textile materials with natural dyes:

1. Fabric preparation: before dyeing, the fabric must be thoroughly cleaned of dirt and impurities. This is important so that the dyes evenly penetrate into the fibers of the fabric and ensure color fastness. To do this, the fabric is usually washed with mild detergents and rinsed in hot water.

2. Staining: staining is the process of pre-treating fabric with special substances called mordents, which help to fix the dye on the fibers and improve the durability of the dye. The most common mordents are alum, iron sulfate and tannins. The fabric is immersed in a mordent solution and kept at a certain temperature for a given time.

3. Preparation of dye: natural dyes are obtained from various sources - plants, insects, minerals. To extract coloring substances, the raw materials are crushed and boiled in water until a saturated dye is obtained. Depending on the desired shade, the concentration and preparation time of the solution may vary.

4. Dyeing: the fabric is immersed in a prepared dye solution. Dyeing is carried out at a certain temperature, which is maintained throughout the process. The aging time of the fabric in the solution depends on the type of dye and the desired color intensity. During dyeing, the fabric is periodically stirred to evenly distribute the dye.

5. Color fixing: after dyeing is completed, the fabric is removed from the solution, thoroughly washed in water to remove excess dye and residual substances. Sometimes, for additional color fixation, the fabric is treated with vinegar or other natural fixatives.

6. Drying: the dyed fabric is dried in the shade or in a well-ventilated room, avoiding direct sunlight, which may cause the color to fade.

To obtain a coloring substance by extraction, 40 g of dry raw materials (nettle, st. john's wort, blueberry, onion) placed in a porcelain glass, poured 500 ml of hot water. They were closed with a lid and heated in a water bath 80-90 °C within 60 minutes. The resulting dyeing solution was cooled at room temperature for 10 minutes, then filtered through one layer of nylon mesh, the remaining raw materials were squeezed out. The volume was brought to the original. The prepared solution can be stored for no more than 2 days. Dyeing was carried out according to figure 2.

Figure 2- Technological scheme of dyeing cotton textile material with extracts of natural dyes

From the analysis of the data obtained, it follows that the developed modes of dyeing fabric with extracts of vegetable dyes provide good strength and resistance of dyeing to wet processing and friction [5,6]. This process requires patience and attention to detail, as each step affects the final result. Despite the complexity, the use of natural dyes makes it possible to obtain unique and environmentally friendly fabrics [7].

Dyeing textiles with natural dyes is not only a return to traditional methods, but also an important step towards more sustainable and environmentally friendly production. Despite certain difficulties, innovations in this area allow you to improve durability and expand the range of available colors.

REFERENCES

1. Carvalho C., Santos G. Sustainability and Biotechnology – Natural or Bio Dyes Resources in Textiles. *Journal of Textile Science & Engineering*, 2016, 6(1), pp. 1-5.
2. Dyeing with Natural Materials: A Comprehensive Guide. *Journal of Sustainable Textiles*, 2023, Vol. 15, No. 2, pp. 101-115.
3. Chungkrang, L., Phukan, A.R. and Kalita, B. Eco-dyeing of wool yarn with *Ziziphus jujuba* Mill. (Ber) and its colour fastness properties. *Journal of Applied and Natural Science*, (2018). 10 (3), pp. 1046 -1052.
4. Daberao, A. M., Kolte, P. P. and Turukmane, R. N. (2016). Cotton Dying with Natural Dye. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 3(8), pp. 157-161.
5. Dogan, S.D. and Akan, M. (2018). A Research on Colours and Fastness Values of Different Materials Dyed with Some Natural Dyes. *International Journal of Materials Science and Applications*, 7(3), pp. 69-74.
6. Guha, A.R. A Review on Sources and Application of Natural Dyes in Textiles. *International Journal of Textile Science*, 2019, 8(2), pp. 38-40.
7. Shukla, D., Vankar, P.S. *Natural Dyes for Textiles, Sources, Chemistry and Applications*. A volume in Woodhead Publishing Series in Textiles, 2017, pp. 141–166.